

ENHANCED FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF EPOXY COMPOSITES WITH IRON OXIDE NANORODS

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ABSTRACT

Two kinds of iron oxide nanorods (FeOOH and Fe₂O₃) were synthesized and surface modified with γ -methacryloxypropyl trimethoxysilane (KH-570). Epoxy (EP) nanocomposites with 1wt% the nanorods were prepared. X-ray diffraction (XRD), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) tests show that FeOOH and Fe₂O₃ nanorods have the purity of 84% and 100%, respectively, and both have uniform one-dimensional nanorod morphology (L=600nm, d=50nm) and rough surface. Fourier transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) tests revealed that KH-570 has successfully modified the iron oxide nanorods by chemical bond. The two modified nanorods have significantly improved the fracture toughness of EP, and the effect of FeOOH nanorods is better than that of Fe₂O₃ nanorods. The fracture critical stress intensity factor (K_{IC}) and the critical stress release rate (G_{IC}) of modified FeOOH/EP are 3.44 MPa·m^{1/2} and 3.3 kJ/m², which are 177% and 735% higher than that of pure EP, respectively. The toughening mechanism was given according to SEM analysis.

1 INTRODUCTION

Epoxy resin (EP) is a kind of thermosetting resins with excellent mechanical properties, which is often used as coatings, adhesives, composite resin matrix in the fields of sports, ships, aerospace and others. However, the high crosslinking of EP not only gives the rigidity and strength of the material, but also limits the plastic deformation of the EP matrix. This characteristic of EP is easy to cause the brittle fracture of products and greatly limits the application of EP. With the general goal of improving the fracture toughness of EP, the reinforcement with nano-sized fillers currently represents an active field of research [1]. The introduction of nanoparticles cause pinning, branching, bridging and deflection of crack, which results in reduction in the crack driving at the crack tip, thus plays an important role in improving the fracture toughness of EP [2]. Khan et al. [3] reported that the nanoparticles with large aspect ratio (lamellar, one-dimensional rod like) are favorable for the bridging and deflection of the crack, which can improve the mechanical properties effectively. Lim et al. [4] prepared EP composites containing 1wt% Al₂O₃ with different shapes. The K_{IC} and G_{IC} of the composites compared to pure EP are increased by 28% and 54% with Al₂O₃ nanorods, respectively. The effect of different shapes of ceria nanoparticles on the mechanical properties of EP had been studied by He et al. [5]. The results show that the composite with high aspect ratio ceria has the highest impact strength of 17.27kJ/m² that is about 4 times that of pure EP.

Whereas, there still remains a great challenge to obtain high-performance EP composites. Interfacial failure between nanoparticles and EP, aggregation of nanoparticles in EP are the main reasons

for the poor performance of composites, thus, it is necessary to modify the nanoparticles [6-9]. Tang et al. [10] showed that the K_{IC} of ozone modified CNTs / EP is 53% higher than that of neat EP and 23% higher than that of unmodified composites when the content of CNTs was 1 wt%. Park et al. [11] studied the EP composites filled 0.5 wt% unmodified and oxyfluorinated CNTs. The results show that the K_{IC} of EP increased by 7.34% and 24.3%, respectively. Tao et al. [1] investigated the effect on 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) on the properties of the EP composites, and found that the K_{IC} and the tensile strength of composites with APTES are 106% and 50% higher than EP when the content of Fe_2O_3 nanoparticles is 4 wt%.

Iron oxyhydroxide (FeOOH) is a typical one-dimensional nanorods. Fe_2O_3 nanorods, which are obtained by dehydrating FeOOH particles, maintain the rod-like morphology of FeOOH. So far, a variety of methods have been employed for synthesizing and modified these nanorods with a mature process [12]. However, few studies have been conducted to improve the fracture toughness of EP by FeOOH and Fe_2O_3 nanorods. Based on this background, in this work, FeOOH was prepared by liquid-phase deposition-air oxidation method, and then dehydrated to obtain Fe_2O_3 nanorods. The iron oxide nanorods were surface modified with γ -methacryloxypropyl trimethoxysilane (KH-570), and then dispersed in EP for preparation of the FeOOH/EP and Fe_2O_3 /EP composites. The influence of kinds and surface treatment of nanorods on the fracture properties of EP were investigated when the iron oxide nanorods content was 1 wt%.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Ferrous chloride tetrahydrate ($FeCl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$) and sodium hydroxide (NaOH) were purchased from Xilong chemical Limited by Share Ltd (China). The silane coupling reagent KH-570 was obtained from Nanjing Youpu Chemical Co., Ltd (China). Epoxy resin (diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A, RIMR 135), and curing agent (modified amine, RIMH 134) were supplied by Hexion Specialty Chemicals Inc (USA).

2.2 Synthesis and surface modification of iron oxide nanorods

The FeOOH nanorods were obtained by the liquid phase oxidation method [13], and then were calcined at 350°C for 1.5h to obtain the Fe_2O_3 nanorods. The surface of iron oxide nanorods was modified by KH-570. For this purpose, KH-570 (the weight ratios of the nanorods to KH-570 was 5: 2) was added in a weak acid aqueous solution with a pH of 3~4. The aqueous solution was mixed with the iron nanorods, followed by ultrasonic dispersion for 0.5h and then mechanical stirring (250 r/min) for 2h at 70°C in water bath. After the mixtures were washed with absolute alcohol by centrifugation (8000r/min, 10min) for 3 times to remove excess KH570, the iron oxide nanorods modified by KH-570 were obtained.

2.3 Preparation of nanocomposites

The iron oxide nanorods (1 wt% of EP) were first dispersed in ethanol, and the suspensions were sonicated for 30 min. Then the suspensions were dropped into EP and mixed with a mechanical stirrer for 2 h at 80 °C. Ethanol was completely removed in a vacuum oven at 100°C for 12 h to obtain the mixtures of the iron oxide nanorods and EP. And then the mixtures and the curing agent (30 wt% of EP) were mixed evenly and then poured into the mold. The nanocomposites were obtained after curing at room temperature for 3h and 80°C for 12 hours.

2.4 Characterization

The composition of iron oxide nanorods was analyzed by X-ray diffraction (XRD, model D8-2-Advance, Germany BRUKER). The thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA, Germany NETZSCH, STA449F3) was used to analyze the thermal stability of iron oxide nanorods and nanocomposites under the argon atmosphere, at the temperature range of 30 to 500°C and at a heating rate of 10 ° C/min. The morphology of the iron oxide nanorods and the composite were investigated using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, model Quanta450FEG, US FEI). Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR, BRUKER, Germany, TENSOR27) test was carried out to characterize the composition of unmodified and modified nanorods. The elemental composition and interfacial interactions were further studied using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, ESCALAB 250Xi, USA Thermo Fisher), under the condition of Al K α , Mono 250 μ m, 200W, pass energy 20 eV, 1.0 eV for full-scan and 0.1 eV for narrow-scan. The fracture critical stress intensity factor (K_{IC}) and the critical stress release rate (G_{IC}) was determined using a single edge notch bend (SENB) test according to ASTM D5045-99 standard and the modified SENB specimens [5].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Characterization of iron oxide nanorods

Figure 1 (a) shows the XRD spectrum of iron oxide nanorods. According to the XRD data of FeOOH, the diffraction peaks at 31.57 °, 42.43 °, 54.83 °, 61.98 ° and 71.79 ° are correspond to the crystal plane (120), (013), (200), (151) and (231) of the standard FeOOH (PDF # 08-0098), respectively. In addition to the FeOOH phase, an extra phase of Fe₃O₄ is further detected. This means that a mixture of FeOOH and Fe₃O₄ were prepared by the liquid - deposited air oxidation method. Combining to TGA of FeOOH in Fig. 2 (b), when the temperature rises to 500 °C, the mass of FeOOH has a weight loss of 8.5%, which is due to the pyrolysis of FeOOH with the product of Fe₂O₃ nanorods at high temperature, as shown in Formula 1. It can be indicated that most of the mixed particles are FeOOH nanorods, about 84% of the mixture.

The diffraction peaks at 45.62 °, 51.43 °, 60.64 °, 77.72 ° and 84.75 ° of Fe₂O₃, which are correspond to the crystal plane (400), (511), (440) of the standard Fe₂O₃ (PDF # 39-1346), respectively. But the other peaks are not observed in the pattern. In contrast to the TGA of Fe₂O₃ in Fig. 2 (b), there is almost no weight loss of the product. This can be understood that the product is relatively pure Fe₂O₃.

The morphology of iron oxides was analyzed by SEM. As shown in Fig 2 (a), FeOOH has a one-dimensional nanorod shape with the length of around 600 nm and the diameter of around 50nm, with uniform rod-like morphology. It is also found that the surface of FeOOH is coated by some nanoparticles with a diameter about 50nm, which makes the surface of nanorods rough. Fig. 3 (b) is the SEM of Fe₂O₃ obtained by calcining FeOOH nanorods at 350 °C for 1.5 h. It can be seen that the Fe₂O₃ nanorods retains the rod-like morphology of FeOOH. Meanwhile, the nanoparticles with a diameter of about 50 nm remain on the surface after the calcination process.

Fig. 3 clearly shows that silane modification process is carried out in two steps. In the first step, the KH-570 hydrolysis occurs in acidic solution followed by hydrogen bonding of the hydrolyzed KH-570 molecules with the -OH on the surface of iron oxide nanorods. Then the silane chains can be covalently

bonded with the surface of nanorods [12], as shown in Fig. 3. In this way a layer of KH-570 can be adsorbed on the surface of nanorods that convert its surface nature to be lipophilic.

Fig.1. (a) XRD pattern and (b) TGA curve of iron oxide nanorods

Fig.2. SEM images of iron oxide nanorods. (a) FeOOH, (b) Fe₂O₃.

Fig.3. A schematic procedure of KH-570 surface modification of iron oxide nanorods.

The effect of KH-570 surface modified iron oxide nanorods was studied by FTIR analysis (Fig. 4). As shown in the spectra, the -OH absorption bands of FeOOH without KH-570 is located at 3434 cm^{-1}

[14], and the peak at 3132 cm^{-1} is attributed to the -OH absorption band of Fe_3O_4 [15]. The -OH stretching vibration of modified FeOOH occurs at 3414 cm^{-1} , which shows slightly red-shift compared with unmodified FeOOH. This may be due to the binding of KH-570 to FeOOH and reduces the energy of -OH. Also, two new peaks appear at 1726 cm^{-1} and 1179 cm^{-1} , which are corresponded to the C=O and Si-O characteristic peaks of KH-570, respectively. The -OH characteristic peaks of unmodified Fe_2O_3 appear at 3438 cm^{-1} , but is weaker than that of FeOOH, which indicates that the amount of -OH on surface is significantly reduced compared to that on the surface of FeOOH. After the surface modification, the -OH characteristic peak of Fe_2O_3 at 3426.70 cm^{-1} obviously becomes wider and stronger, which indicates that the amount of -OH on Fe_2O_3 is increased. In addition, the new absorption bands at 1726 cm^{-1} and 1179 cm^{-1} are related to C=O and Si-O of KH570, respectively. The result of FTIR spectra confirms that KH-570 has successfully modified the iron oxide nanorods by chemical reaction.

Fig.4. FTIR spectra of the unmodified and modified iron oxide nanorods

The unmodified and modified iron oxide nanorods with KH-570 were further analyzed with XPS, and the results are shown in Figs. 5-7 and Table 1. According to the full XPS spectrum of unmodified and modified FeOOH shown in Fig. 5 (a), it can be found that the point of Si2p appears at the binding energy of 100.09 eV, as shown in Figure 6 (a), and the content of Si is 2.51 wt% (Table 1). By comparing the difference between the spectra of unmodified and modified FeOOH, it can be found that the absorption peak of C1s with modified FeOOH is obviously increased, while the absorption peaks of Fe2p and O1s are decreased. The content of O and Fe on the surface of FeOOH nanorods have changed from 41.25% and 12.09% to 36.79% and 2.67% after the modification, respectively, which are decreased by 4.46% and 9.42% when modified with KH-570. While the amount of C is increased by 11.36%. The reasons for peak intensity change are that the addition of KH-570 introduces more C and Si to the surface of FeOOH and the weakened signals of Fe2p and O1s depend on the identifying the surface elements and adsorption density function of XPS [16]. Fig. 7(a) shows the electron binding energy of Fe2p of unmodified and modified FeOOH, in which binding energy is decreased from 709.97 to 709.90 after the modification, which may be due to the dehydration reaction of FeOOH and KH-570. In addition, the Fe-O-Si has higher electronegativity than Fe-O-H, which leads Fe2p to adsorb small amount of negative

charge, and causes the Fe2p layer of electrons to reduce the binding energy.

Fig. 5 (b) shows the XPS spectrums of unmodified and modified Fe₂O₃ nanorods. After the modification of KH-570, the absorption peak of Si2p appears with the binding energy of 104.32eV and the content of 4.42wt%. Similar to FeOOH, the absorption peaks of Fe2p and O1s on Fe₂O₃ are decreased, and the contents of Fe and O element due to the addition of KH-570. The electron binding energy of Fe2p of modified Fe₂O₃ is 711.18eV, which is 0.11eV higher than that of the unmodified Fe2p of Fe₂O₃. And this change indicates that the chemical bond Fe-O-Si between KH-570 and Fe₂O₃ nanorods is formed instead of the chemical bond Fe-O-H [17]. According to the above, it further shows that KH-570 has successfully modified iron oxide nanorods by chemical reaction.

Fig.5 XPS spectra of iron oxide unmodified and modified with KH-570.

(a) FeOOH, (b) Fe₂O₃.

Table1 Binding energy and surface content of unmodified and modified iron oxide nanorods

Nanorods	Binding energy/eV				Surface content (wt%)			
	Fe2p	O1s	C1s	Si2p	Fe2p	O1s	C1s	Si2p
Unmodified FeOOH	709.97	529.07	283.80	-	12.09	41.25	46.66	-
Modified FeOOH	709.90	529.70	283.25	100.09	2.67	36.79	58.02	2.51
Unmodified Fe ₂ O ₃	711.07	531.02	286.04	-	30.48	49.15	20.37	-
Modified Fe ₂ O ₃	711.18	533.74	287.17	104.32	17.72	30.61	47.25	4.42

Fig.6. Binding energy change of modified Si2p. (a) FeOOH; (b) Fe₂O₃.

Fig.7. Binding energy change of unmodified and modified Fe2p. (a) FeOOH; (b) Fe₂O₃.

3.2 Fracture toughness of nanocomposites

In this work, the effect of unmodified and modified iron oxide nanorods on fracture toughness of EP is demonstrated by K_{IC} and G_{IC} . As shown in Table 2, K_{IC} and G_{IC} of neat EP were 1.24 MPa·m^{1/2} and 0.44 kJ/m², which are obviously higher than the composites with unmodified iron oxide nanorods. It is revealed the addition of nanorods without KH-570 does not play a role of toughening the fracture toughness of EP, which is the same as the results reported by Tao et al. [1]. It may be mainly attributed to the poor dispersion of the nanorods in the composites and weak interface interaction between the nanorods and the EP, which are shown in the next fracture surface morphology analysis. But it is noted that the fracture toughness of the composites with the modified nanorods are markedly better than that of EP, especially for that of the modified FeOOH/EP composites. The K_{IC} and G_{IC} of modified FeOOH/EP are 3.44 MPa·m^{1/2} and 3.30 kJ/m², which are 177% and 735% higher than that of neat EP, respectively. These improvement of FeOOH/EP composites are even 133% and 607% higher than that of CNTs/EP reported by Ma [18]. The K_{IC} and G_{IC} of modified Fe₂O₃/EP are 17% and 9% higher than that of neat EP in this work and 32% higher than the K_{IC} in the work by Tao et al. [1].

In order to further explain the toughening effect of iron oxide nanorods on EP, the fracture surface morphology of composites was analyzed by SEM. Fig. 8 (a) shows the fracture surface of pure EP, in which the crack tip is smooth and without any fillers. Compared with neat EP, the fracture surfaces of composites with unmodified nanorods are rougher and appears different cracks deflection induced by nanorods, as shown in Fig. 8 (b, d). Besides, there are some voids in the surface of the composites due to the pull-out of nanorods. This phenomena imply that the interface adhesion between unmodified iron oxide and EP is relatively weak, which is consistent to our speculation above. The nanorods have led the energy to be dissipated and play an important role in improvement of the fracture toughness of EP. Unfortunately, due to the interface defects between nanoparticles and EP, the unmodified iron oxide nanorods does not achieve the purpose of toughening.

The fracture surface morphology of modified nanocomposites are shown in Fig. 8 (c, e). It can be seen from the images that the surfaces of composites with KH-570 are much rougher than that of neat EP and there are no voids in the surfaces. These confirm that the addition of KH-570 improved the interfacial between nanorods and EP. Fig. 8 (c) shows the fracture surface of the modified FeOOH/EP composites, in which there are not only distributed the ordinary cracks like unmodified composite, but

also evenly spread the small cracks like fish scales. As can be seen, the small fish scale-like cracks are caused by breaking of FeOOH nanorods, and it represents the good dispersion of modified FeOOH that induces the marked plastic deformation of EP. The fracture of nanocomposites is always accompanied by the pull out, breaking and debonding of nanorods. These behaviors cause deflected, bridged, terminated of nanorods and plastic deformation of the resin matrix, which all absorb a large amount of crack tip energy and play the role of toughening the matrix [3, 19]. Filling the modified FeOOH in EP, a complex network has been formed because of the rod-like morphology of FeOOH. Thus, more pull-out, breaking and debonding of the FeOOH nanorods are accompanied, as shown in Fig. 9 (a). Because the addition of KH-570 cause breaking of FeOOH nanorods rather than pull out and debonding, which has consumed a part of energy at the tip of the crack. As breaking nanorods generally need absorb greater energy and the plastic deformation of the EP is also induced, the energy of the crack is further consumed to more effectively toughen EP. The toughening mechanisms are almost the same as that proposed in the literatures [3, 18].

The surface of modified Fe₂O₃/EP composites also presents cracks of varying size in Fig. 8 (e), but the distribution of small cracks is not uniform, which implies the dispersibility of Fe₂O₃ nanorods in EP is obviously poorer than FeOOH nanorods even with the help of KH-570. This can be attributed to the different states of iron nanorods in the composites preparation, in which are FeOOH slurry for FeOOH/EP composites and dry powder of Fe₂O₃ for Fe₂O₃/EP composites. That is severe secondary agglomeration of Fe₂O₃ nanorods occurs when FeOOH slurry is dried and calcinated to produce Fe₂O₃ nanorods. The toughening mechanism in the literatures [2, 20] is that the more uniform dispersion of nanoparticles, the better fracture properties of the nanocomposites. As shown in the Fig.9 (b), a part of Fe₂O₃ nanorods are agglomerated in the EP, which makes a region of nanorods free in EP. In this case, the cracks pass through the region as soon as possible and break through the nanocomposites due to the less pulling out, breaking and debonding of the nanorods. The fracture toughness of modified FeOOH/EP composite is better than that of modified Fe₂O₃/EP composites. Besides, there are obvious traces of Fe₂O₃ nanorods debonding, which represents interface between modified Fe₂O₃ nanorods and EP is lower than that between modified FeOOH and EP because of the deference in KH570 modification effect as analyzed in FTIR and XPS. This is another reason for the differences in fracture toughness of modified FeOOH/EP composites and modified Fe₂O₃/EP composites.

Table 2 The fracture toughness of iron oxide/ EP composites

Materials	K _{IC} (MPa·m ^{1/2})	K _{IC} /K _{IC, M}	G _{IC} (kJ/m ²)	G _{IC} / G _{IC, M}
EP	1.24±0.2	1.00	0.44±0.14	1.00
unmodified FeOOH/EP	0.96±0.07	0.77	0.26±0.04	0.59
modified FeOOH/EP	3.44±0.11	2.77	3.28±0.22	7.45
unmodified Fe ₂ O ₃ /EP	1.04±0.20	0.84	0.31±0.13	0.70
modified Fe ₂ O ₃ /EP	1.46±0.22	1.18	0.48±0.19	1.09

Figure 8. Fracture morphology of nanocomposites.

(a) EP; (b) Unmodified FeOOH/EP; (c) Unmodified Fe₂O₃/EP;
(d) Modified FeOOH/EP; (e) Modified Fe₂O₃/EP;

Figure 9. Schematic diagram of iron oxide nanorods toughening EP.

(a) FeOOH/EP, (b) Fe₂O₃/EP.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, two common nanoparticles FeOOH nanorods and Fe₂O₃ nanorods with rough surface and uniform morphology, which can significantly improve the fracture toughness, was first introduced in toughening EP. As there is less effect on the fracture toughness of EP when added unmodified nanorods, the effective surface modification of iron oxide nanorods has been achieved by the silane coupling agent γ -methacryloxypropyl trimethoxysilane (KH-570). Due to the addition of KH-570 enhanced the interfacial between nanorods and EP, the modified nanorods play an effective role to improve the fracture toughness of EP, especially for the modified FeOOH nanorods. The K_{IC} and G_{IC} of modified FeOOH/EP are 3.44MPa.m^{1/2} and 3.3 kJ/m², which are 177% and 735% higher than that of neat EP, respectively. The enhancement in fracture toughness of EP with FeOOH nanorods is the most effective compared to the reported that in the EP composites in a low range of filler content below 10wt%. The reason is mainly attributed to the better dispersion of FeOOH and the KH570 modification of FeOOH, which improved the interfacial bonding strength between EP and FeOOH. In addition, the rod-like morphology of FeOOH is also important for the toughening. The fracture toughening mechanisms of the composites mainly show crack bridging, the nanorods rupture, debonding of nanorods and matrix plastic deformation.

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REFERENCES

- [1] T. Sun, H. Fan, Z. Wang, X. Liu, Z. Wu, Modified nano Fe₂O₃-epoxy composite with enhanced mechanical properties, *Materials & Design*, **87**, 2015, pp.10-16.
- [2] H.Y. Liu, G.T. Wang, Y.W. Mai, Y. Zeng, On fracture toughness of nano-particle modified epoxy, *Composites Part B Engineering*, **42**, 2011, pp. 2170-2175.
- [3] S.U. Khan, J.R. Pothnis, J.K. Kim, Effects of carbon nanotube alignment on electrical and mechanical properties of epoxy nanocomposites, *Composites Part A Applied Science & Manufacturing*, **49**, 2013, pp. 26–34.
- [4] S.H. Lim, K.Y. Zeng, C.B. He, Morphology, tensile and fracture characteristics of epoxy-alumina nanocomposites, *Materials Science & Engineering A*, **527**, 2010. pp. 5670-5676.
- [5] Xiaoqiang, Dengsong, Zhang, Hongrui, Jianhui, Fang, Liyi, Shape and size effects of ceria nanoparticles on the impact strength of ceria epoxy resin composites, *Journal of particles (PARTICUOLOGY)*, **09**, 2011, pp. 80-85.
- [6] K.A. Masser, E.D. Bain, F.L. Beyer, A.M. Savage, J.H. Yu, J.L. Lenhart, Influence of nano-scale morphology on impact toughness of epoxy blends, *Polymer*, **103**, 2016, pp. 337-346.
- [7] J. Baller, N. Becker, M. Ziehmer, M. Thomassey, B. Zielinski, U. Müller, R. Sanctuary, Interactions between silica nanoparticles and an epoxy resin before and during network formation, *Polymer*, **50**, 2009, pp. 3211-3219.
- [8] R. Bao, S. Yan, Y. Qin, M. Lu, Improving thermal conductivity and shear strength of carbon nanotubes/epoxy composites via thiol-ene click reaction, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **134**, (2016).

- [9] Y. Geng, M.Y. Liu, J. Li, X.M. Shi, J.K. Kim, Effects of surfactant treatment on mechanical and electrical properties of CNT/epoxy nanocomposites, *Composites Part A Applied Science & Manufacturing*, **39**, 2008, pp. 1876-1883.
- [10] L.C. Tang, H. Zhang, J.H. Han, X.P. Wu, Z. Zhang, Fracture mechanisms of epoxy filled with ozone functionalized multi-wall carbon nanotubes, *Composites Science & Technology*, **72**, 2011, pp. 7-13.
- [11] S.J. Park, H.J. Jeong, C. Nah, A study of oxyfluorination of multi-walled carbon nanotubes on mechanical interfacial properties of epoxy matrix nanocomposites, *Materials Science & Engineering A*, **385**, 2004, pp. 13-16.
- [12] A.A. Javidparvar, B. Ramezanzadeh, E. Ghasemi, Effects of surface morphology and treatment of iron oxide nanoparticles on the mechanical properties of an epoxy coating, *Progress in Organic Coatings*, **90**, 2016, pp. 10-20.
- [13] C. Sudakar, G.N. Subbanna, T.R.N. Kutty, Effect of anions on the phase stability of γ -FeOOH nanoparticles and the magnetic properties of gamma-ferric oxide derived from lepidocrocite, *Journal of Physics & Chemistry of Solids*, **64**, 2003, pp. 2337-2349.
- [14] P. Ou, G. Xu, Z. Ren, X. Hou, G. Han, Hydrothermal synthesis and characterization of uniform α -FeOOH nanowires in high yield, *Materials Letters*, **62**, 2008, pp. 914-917.
- [15] Wang, Rujuan, Ma, Yingxia, Lu, Cuiping, Li, Tao, Du, Xueyan, Preparation and Adsorption Property of Glutathione Magnetic Molecularly Imprinted Polymers, *Acta Chimica Sinica*, **72**, 2014, pp. 577.
- [16] Y. Zhou, Y. Zhang, G. Li, T. Jiang, Effects of metal cations on the fulvic acid (FA) adsorption onto natural iron oxide in iron ore pelletizing process, *Powder Technology*, **302**, 2016, pp. 90-99.
- [17] P. Hong, Z. Xiao, K. Huang, X.U. Huibi, Modification of Fe₃O₄ Magnetic Nanoparticles by L-dopa or Dopamine as an Enzyme Support, *Journal of Wuhan University of Technology-Mater. Sci. Ed.*, **23**, 2008, pp. 480-485.
- [18] C. Ma, H.Y. Liu, X. Du, L. Mach, F. Xu, Y.W. Mai, Fracture resistance, thermal and electrical properties of epoxy composites containing aligned carbon nanotubes by low magnetic field, *Composites Science & Technology*, **114**, 2015, pp. 126-135.
- [19] F.H. Gojny, M.H.G. Wichmann, B. Fiedler, K. Schulte, Influence of different carbon nanotubes on the mechanical properties of epoxy matrix composites – A comparative study, *Composites Science & Technology*, **65**, 2005, pp. 2300-2313.
- [20] B.C. Kim, W.P. Sang, G.L. Dai, Fracture toughness of the nano-particle reinforced epoxy composite, *Composite Structures*, **86**, 2008, pp. 69-77.